

Drama, Ethnicity And National Integration In John Iwuh's *Birthright: An Appraisal*

Salifu, Musa¹, Mohammed- Kabir Jibril Imam²

¹Theatre Arts Department,
Kogi State University, Anyigba
08140746543/ 08173008295
Mcdegreat@Gmail.Com

²Theatre Arts Department,
Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri, Imo State
08037355827/08051123410
kabirjib@gmail.com / kabirm96@yahoo.com

Abstract

Nigeria, the largest and most populous African nation, perhaps, due to her multi-lingual, multi-cultural and multi-ethnic nature, has been bedeviled with many challenges such as tribalism, communal rivalries, nepotism and ethnocentrism among others, since she got her independence on October 1st, 1960. This has hindered the development and advancement of the nation. Drama on the other hand, has been seen as a concrete instrument for national integration. The aforementioned challenges have over the years degenerated into cases of dishonest and disunity which at many occasions created violent scenes across the country because of lack of unity among the avalanche of ethnic groups. The study adopts the instrument of content analysis of the qualitative research methodology by delving into the play and analyse the content by appraising the issues therein. The result reveals that many effective means have been used to foster national integration in the country among which is theatre and drama. The study concludes that drama and theatre are strong vehicles to help in the integration of a nation with gravious unity in diversity and differences. The study recommends among others that the means of drama and theatre should be explored to synergize the differences for a better society.

Introduction

Drama is a re-enactment of life with the aim of, apart from the others, providing entertainment and life-changing lessons for the audience. Drama has equally been viewed as the mirror of

the society. It is a slice of life represented on stage by actors and actresses. Through drama and theatre, societal experiences are shown before the audience. Drama and theatre mirror the society; they either present the society as it

were, or correct it. Theatre and Drama hold the responsibilities to correct the societal ills. In this vein, Amirikpa posits that: “drama possesses redeeming societal values and the onerous responsibility to correct the ills of the society.” (77)

Nigerian theatre and drama have been, right from the pre-colonial days, playing important roles in the society. The modern Nigerian theatre and drama for instance, which emerges following the coming of the British into the country have discussed many socio-political and cultural problems facing the country. Nigerian playwrights like Wole Soyinka, J.P. Clark, Femi Osofisan, John Iwuh and the others have portrayed Nigerian societal problems in their various plays providing solutions to the problems for national integration, peace, stability and development.

It is based on this backdrop that the paper focuses on Nigerian theatre and drama, ethnicity and national integration: Appraising John Iwuh’s *Birthright*. The paper intends to investigate how playwrights through their ingenuity try to mirror the Nigerian society in their artistic creations. These dramatists in various ways present that despite multi-ethnicity and unity in diversity, all we need is understanding our differences and coming together as one for a better living and development.

Social Integration Theory

Social integration is how people from different groups in society come together. And how is this maintained? In sociology, the concept of social integration refers to a situation where minority groups come together or are incorporated into mainstream society. Though, we should note, this doesn't mean in a forceful way.

Social integration also refers to a process of largely agreeing on a shared system of meaning, language, culture, and the like. This doesn't mean there aren't any differences, but that we kind of agree to live together and, at least to an extent, feel part of a larger community. Increased social integration helps reduce conflict in society, and it can help us feel more connected to our community. Let's talk about some of the ways that influential sociologists have thought about social integration.

Émile Durkheim, considered one of the founders of modern sociology, had a lot to say about social integration. He was one of the first to explore the concept in a book called *The Division of Labor in Society*, written in 1892. Durkheim considered society to be the collective consciousness of people. In other words, the way we think, feel, and behave is influenced by society in a major way. But, how do we remain a cohesive whole and avoid too much conflict?

Durkheim came up with a couple different types of social integration, which he referred to as kinds of solidarity. Durkheim believes that society exerted a powerful force on individuals. People's norms, beliefs, and values make up a collective consciousness, or a shared way of understanding and behaving in the world. The collective consciousness binds individuals together and creates social integration.

First, mechanical solidarity is what binds more primitive, or smaller, societies together. In this kind of solidarity, it's things like kinship and shared beliefs that hold us together. We're integrated because we're all pretty similar. In more advanced societies, we see the emergence of organic solidarity. In a more complex society, a complex division of labor requires us to rely on each other more. This kind of interdependence creates increased social integration, instead of simply our similarities.

But what if we don't achieve this integration? In Durkheim's view, this leads to a problem known as anomie, or a sense of feeling very disconnected from others and from our community. Decreased social integration leads to anomie and, potentially, conflict. Now that we know a little about the foundation of social integration theory.

Overview of Nigerian Theatre and Drama

Like other parts of African continent, theatre and drama exist in pre-colonial Nigerian societies. The traditional Nigerian theatre and drama is an indigenous cultural institution nurtured in the various kingdoms, communities and villages in Nigeria during the pre-colonial days. There is no gainsaying that Nigerian theatre and drama emanate from the avalanche of cultural festivals we have in these communities and kingdoms. According to Yemi Ogunbiyi,

The specific origins of Nigerian theatre and drama are speculative. What is however, not speculative...is the existence, in many Nigerian societies, of a robust theatrical tradition. The primitive root of that tradition must be sought in the numerous religious rituals and festivals that exist in many Nigerian communities...as an expression of the relationship between man, society and nature, drama arose out of fundamental human needs in dawn of human civilisation and has continued to express those needs ever since: which is to say, that Nigerian theatre and drama originated with the Nigerian himself... (2)

Drama thus is a strong part of the peoples' culture, tradition and belief system. Corroborating this, Inyanda and Adama opine that:

Traditional African theatre is the indigenous form of theatre which comprises communal events in the forms of masquerade performance, myths, ritual institutions, festivals etc. Its elements are deeply rooted in the culture and cosmology of the African society. (3)

In line with the above, pre-colonial Nigerian indigenous theatre and drama, as an African traditional theatre comprises storytelling, myths, ritual institutions, festivals. There have been heated debates on whether drama and theatre exist in pre-colonial Africa and to what extent it could be distinguished from mere rituals. African theatrical forms like masquerade institutions and many others can provide an answer to this. However, broad differentiation can be made between drama and ritual as opined by Yemi Ogunbiyi that, "...broad distinction s can be made between ritual and drama, for while ritual is essentially functional, drama is not, at least not in the sense of immediate results and consequences beyond itself" (4).

Masquerade institutions, festivals, storytelling and other elements that form African traditional theatre and drama make use of theatrical components such as stage, costume, makeup, actor, and actress. Oyin in Inyanda and Egwu posit that:

When one watches a traditional African festival, one is immediately struck by the facts that one has been exposed to a dramatic experience.

African traditional performance is an indigenous cultural institution. A set of art forms nurtured on the African soil over the centuries. (3)

This espouses us to the fact that the pre-colonial Nigerian societies have ancestral ceremonies and other cultural feasts where Nigerian traditional drama and theatre is said to have emanated.

Nigerian modern drama and theatre is a brain child of the nation's colonial experience. Simply put, modern African theatre and drama began to emerge in Nigeria and African continent at large when the British came to the continent. They brought, apart from business transaction, ideas, religion, western education and their mode of theatre and drama. According to Amirikpa:

The movement from the traditional ritual masquerade festival theatre to the modern theatrical art form has been informed by a number of factors such as the advent of colonial rule, the introduction of western education, the incursion of Christianity and Islam, and the money economy which promoted material values and morality of old. The move was to dismiss everything traditionally African as heathen and barbaric. European value systems were foisted upon the newly educated African elites who were made to denigrate their African heritage with indignity. (44)

Without iota of doubt, the colonial experiences such as western education and the other ideas brought by the colonialists to Nigeria and the quest for further study by some Nigerian elites some centuries ago, were responsible for the emergence of modern drama and theatre in the country. These experiences produced the country's early generations of theatre artists and playwrights like Hubert Ogunde, E.K Ogunmola, EneHenshaw, J.P Clark, Wole Soyinka and the others.

Theatre and Society

Theatre, right from the early days, has portrayed many societal issues leading to peaceful co-existence of man and societal development. Bamidele submits that: "theatre serves as a criticizing agent. This implies that drama engages in perfection of human society be it social and political" (15). It is in line with the above that Agoro posits that:

Theatre can be seen as a means of interpreting all our common experiences within the society. It can teach us more about the ways in which people live... through drama, a group can create and explore a different society with norms and values. (51)

Drama can equally be used as a vehicle of change and transformation. Validating Akorede's position that: "The dramatist is the

watch-man in his society. He is the people's secret police. His duty is to shift out information... to bring the culprits to the people's court..." (56).

The performers reflect the situations of varying degrees as they concern the society for societal transformation and development. These issues can either be social, political and economic which are unavoidable. Theatre artist employed the analysis of societal problems as an effective weapon in raising the consciousness of the people towards the nation's ethnic, social, political and economic problems. That is why Illah asserts that: "theatre aims to transform the world, its aim is to make existence more bearable, it aims to simplify man's life and to identify man with nature" (15). Without doubt, the relevance of theatre and drama is seen in its roles in portraying socio-cultural, political and economic realities of the society.

Thus, theatre and society are indispensable. They are inseparable because, theatre needs the society for raw materials and the society needs theatre for sustainability. Any attempt to separate them would lead to the destruction of both. That is why the artist views himself as teacher, prophet, philosopher and educator of the society.

Nigerian Theatre and Drama, Ethnicity and National Integration

Apart from the Hausa/Fulani, Yoruba and Igbo, which they say are the main major ethnic groups in Nigeria, as Kolawole opines that: “Ethnicity presupposes cultural pluralism and it entails a feeling of superiority of one group over the other. This feeling becomes premise for exploiting and relegating the seemingly inferior group” (235), the country houses many other ethnic groups like Igala, Urhobo, Itsekiri, Isang, Tiv, Idoma to name but a few. Each of these ethnic groups, from studies over the years, struggles for its interest and achievement; leading to the issue of ethnicity, the brain child of tribalism and threat of national disintegration in the country. Adell Patton succinctly captures it thus: “‘Tribe’ refers to a group forming a single linguistic cluster with loyalty to the group, whose agenda is to foster political action or to follow an agenda favorable to its own group’ (3). He further acknowledges that: “The consequences that such an agenda might have on the nation notwithstanding” (Patton 3), have equally lead to economic, social and political problems in the country. Also, these problems have degenerated to what we are witnessing as Fulani/herdsmen clash or Boko Haram saga which has been revealed as having political undertone. This, Patton states that: “These factors lead to the category of ethnicity based on

inter-cultural group rivalry that now replaced the former “tribalism””. (4) This problem has been there right from the colonial days. This is why Achebe says that:

The British were well aware of the inter-ethnic tension and posturing for power among the three main ethnic groups. By 1951, they had divided the country into the Northern, Eastern and Western Regions, with their own respective houses of assembly, to contain this rising threat. There was also what many thought as an inane house of chiefs – a poor copy of the House of Lord of the British Parliament. (47)

The Nigerian problem of ethnicity which started right from the nation’s colonial days has until today remains the major challenge facing the nation. This is why Chinwe posits that: “There is no gainsaying that the greatest challenge facing the country is the threat to its national unity. The reason is not hard to explain because Nigeria is a multi-ethnic nation with diverse cultures and traditions” (1). There may be threat to its unity as people become aware of how they are being marginalized as it is contained in Mogu’s position that: “...it is clear that the status quo cannot be sustained since the people become aware and gradually bound to proffer workable and enduring solutions as a way to establish genuine democracy” (223).

Because of the damage the problem has caused the nation over the years, many institutions such as theatre and drama, annual cultural festivals, National Youths Service Corps (NYSC) and a host of others, have been used to preach the need for national integration to citizens of the nation; the need to kill ethnicity and tribalism where any citizen of the country could live and work in a place of his choice without facing ethnic discrimination. It was posited that:

...the major ethnic groups (Hausa, Yoruba and Ibo), have been in the driving seat of the political machine for a greater part of the period after independence in 1960, while the minority ethnic groups have been in the lurch, feeling marginalized, neglected and vulnerable. Misgiving remain deep-seated and the 'unity in diversity' cliché remains a mirage. A traumatic aspect of the democratic process is that once you reside outside your place of origin you remain disenfranchised. (Eugene Aniah 91)

Over the years, Nigerian theatre and drama have been designed within the framework of national integration and development. Nigerian theatre and drama play a role in uniting the different ethnic groups in the country. The nation's theatre artists have produced many drama and theatre portraying their different cultures, languages and traditions covering themes that can promote national unity, peace and development. A good example of such drama is John Iwuh's *Birthright*.

Biography of John Iwuh

John Iwuh Enyeribe is a Nigerian playwright, theatre personality, scholar, essayist, lecturer and an associate professor of scenography and performance aesthetics. John Iwuh, the winner of ANA/DDC/JP Clark National Literary prize for Drama, 2008, is the author of *The Village Lamb* (2007), *Ashes and Daydreams* (2007), *Spell Bound* (2009) and *Birthright* (2016). His works mostly centered on socio-political situations facing his nation, Nigeria.

Synopsis of John Iwuh's *Birthright*

The play opens with a prologue that gives the total atmosphere or the mode of the play. It is a tale of destruction, bloodshed and unpleasant psychological experiences of war.

The play is set in a land called Obodonile. Apart from the major three geographical areas like Ndi-Ala, Ndi-Ugwu and Ndi-Nda, Obodonile houses other areas like Enumiri and the others; and each of the geographical areas belongs to a particular ethnic group.

Sadly, extreme ethnic recognition and greedy desire for power breeds conflict among the people. Ndi-Ala, the region of the land where the major sources of the land's income comes from wants to be on its own; and the government of Obodonile says no to that. This caused the war that claims millions of lives in the play.

Analysis of *Birthright*

The play is a documentation of the history of Nigerian/Biafran Civil War, its causes and the effect of the war on the nation. Like Obodonile nation in the play, pre-colonial Nigeria was divided into kingdoms; each of the kingdoms with a particular ethnic group and tribe.

But the British came and for her own interest brought the nation's various kingdoms together making it one nation, Nigeria, without considering the problems that may arise thereafter. Like one of the characters in the play points out the discrimination that exists among the different ethnic groups in Nigeria:

Nwaka: I know it will get to this point... Go and meet Oyigbo who joined the baboon and the chimpanzee together as brothers to come and advocate on their birthrights... (45)

Like in the play, ethnicity and tribalism cum power – struggle were the things that bred Nigerian problems which led to the nation's civil war. The various ethnic groups comprises Hausa/Fulani, Yoruba, Igbo, Igala and the others, like Ndi-Ala, Ndi-Nda and Ndi-Ugwu in the play, failed to manage their differences. They failed to recognize that there is unity in diversity. Thus, each of the ethnic groups, deserving its own progress and forgetting the fact that there cannot be progress without unity and peace. As the narrator aptly captures it :

Narrator: ... Leadership is not about money, it is exercising authority with common sense for the good of all. There can't be peace without love. Who is your enemy? Is he the person who dresses differently from the way you do? Is he the one who speaks a language different from yours? Or is he the person who lives several miles away from your village... (24)

The various ethnic groups failed to identify their enemy or friend due to ethnicity thereby permitted ethnicity, tribalism and greedy desire for power to cause them woes. As Eze, one of the characters in the play puts it:

Eze: The quest for power was the reason for Obonile – Ndiala war... (75)

Achumba another character in play also sees that:

Achumba: ... the war caused by the struggle for power by men of the capital city... (62)

Alas, the Obodonile – Ndiala war, the figuration of Nigerian – Biafran was which was caused by greedy leaders fueled by ethnicity, sentiments and tribalism leads to destruction of many lives and properties. The narrator in the play reports thus:

Narrator: They are defeated... The people have lost everything; wives, husbands, children, they've lost jobs and houses... (39)

The play has all the elements that can promote Nigerian national integration. It reveals the

causes of the country's civil war and the need to avoid its repetition. It shows the effect of war in order to caution the nation about war.

Achumba: The war attacked and sucked the blood of everyone of us like a mosquito. The man who lost his wife is not different from the woman who lost her husband... (56)

Reverend: I have no congregation. I have refugees with missing arms and legs. Many of them are deaf from explosions while many could hardly see. (49)

The above dialogues in the play have power to caution the nation against war; they show the effects of war.

Also, the play condemns ethnicity, sentiments and tribalism that have been the major challenge of the nation over the years; and call for national unity and love.

Nze: Is it the language? Even our brother from Ebonyi can hardly hear our dialect without straining his ears. Is it our complexion? Even the white man in his selfishness came here and showed love... Yet the fraction of a broken calabash endures more water than our palms... (15)

The above dialogue without doubt cautions the nation against ethnicity and tribalism. Also, the below dialogues reveals the effect of ethnicity on our noble nation

Narrator: Selfish realization in any form will either break homes or build homes. Consciousness will

either make us selfish or patriotic. Even love knows whom to hate. So, it makes us humanists or beasts. Extreme ethnic recognition rather than make us one breads prejudice... (72)

The play finally advocates for unity, love and collective struggle for national development.

This is shown in Achumba's dialogue:

Achumba: ... what belongs to my father belongs to all his children. Obodonile is our father once again; let Ndi-Ugwu dream, let Ndi-Nda dream, let Ndi-Ala join in the dream... let everyone's dream take his brother into account. That is what is important... (57)

Therefore, John Iwuh's *Birthright* is an advocacy on national integration. The play, if staged across the nation, has the capacity and pomposity to promote national unity, peace and development.

Recommendations

From the study, it obvious that ethnicity, tribe and group are not parameters for disintegration rather, they should be seen as strong instruments for integration and advancement in our differences.

Drama and theatre should be seen as vehicles that can be used to foster and nurture integration amidst our differences and diversity.

It must also be noted that God in his infinite wisdom who has brought the different ethnic

groups together as a country has good intention for his creatures. Any leader who tries to discriminate will be causing disunity among the people.

Whether majority ethnic groups or minority ethnic groups, we are all indispensable and that is why any attempt to disintegrate these groups would always lead to bloodshed or war in some cases. Therefore, no attempt should be made towards disintegration. This will be an aberration.

It is instructive to note that plays like John Iwuh's *Birthright* should be permitted on our University theatre stages and equally effort should be geared towards performing such plays outside the four walls of the University. Such plays should be taken to found spaces for performance for unstructured audiences. By so doing we will be spreading the good messages of such plays.

Conclusion

This paper to some extent has shown the functions of theatre and drama in the society. The paper ascertained that Drama and theatre play important roles in the society. The problem of threat to national integration that has been facing Nigeria as a nation over the years can be solved and resolved through drama and theatre. If the Nigerian government pays more attention

to the use of drama and theatre in addressing this problem, national unity is assured.

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